

Teleportation-Based Quantum Error Correction under Noisy Channels

Aparna Sasi

School of Electronics Systems and Automation
Kerala University of Digital Sciences, Innovation and Technology
Thiruvananthapuram, India

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Abstract

Quantum teleportation is a fundamental protocol in quantum communication that enables the transfer of an unknown quantum state using shared entanglement and classical communication. In realistic quantum hardware, teleportation circuits are affected by decoherence, gate imperfections, and operational noise, limiting their practical fidelity. This work presents a numerical study of teleportation-based quantum error correction (QEC) under realistic noise conditions. The three-qubit repetition code, Steane's code, and Shor's code are analyzed using density-matrix simulations with bit-flip, phase-flip, and amplitude-damping noise [4]. Ideal teleportation effectively acts as an identity channel, yielding the same logical fidelity as direct QEC, while noise in the teleportation channel introduces additional errors that degrade performance. The results demonstrate a clear trade-off between circuit complexity and error-correction capability in noisy intermediate-scale quantum devices and clarify the role of teleportation in practical quantum error correction schemes.

Keywords: Quantum teleportation; Quantum error correction; Logical fidelity; Noise modeling; Qiskit simulation

1 Introduction

Quantum teleportation is a central protocol in quantum information science, enabling the transfer of an unknown quantum state without physically moving the carrier qubit [2]. It forms a foundational component of quantum communication networks, distributed quantum computation, and modular quantum architectures. In idealized theoretical settings, teleportation achieves unit fidelity [2]. However, realistic quantum hardware is subject to decoherence, gate errors, and crosstalk, which significantly reduce teleportation fidelity.

Quantum error correction (QEC) provides a systematic framework for protecting quantum information against such noise by encoding logical qubits into entangled states of multiple physical qubits [4]. Among the earliest and most widely studied codes are the three-qubit

Figure 1: Schematic of the standard quantum teleportation protocol. An unknown quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ held by Alice is transferred to Bob using a shared entangled Bell pair $|\Phi^+\rangle$ and the transmission of classical measurement outcomes through a classical communication channel.

repetition code, which protects against bit-flip errors, Shor’s code, which corrects both bit-flip and phase-flip errors, and Steane’s code, which corrects arbitrary single-qubit errors using the stabilizer formalism [4].

Teleportation-based quantum error correction has been explored as a strategy for mitigating noise in quantum communication channels and distributed architectures [1, 6, 7]. In particular, teleportation has been shown to provide a direct interface between physical qubits and logical code spaces, enabling the transfer of encoded quantum information [6].

However, in many existing studies, ideal teleportation is implicitly assumed, thereby obscuring the impact of noise introduced during teleportation operations themselves. In near-term noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) devices, the increased circuit depth and qubit overhead associated with sophisticated QEC codes may offset their theoretical advantages, especially when teleportation-induced errors are taken into account [3].

In this work, we present a unified numerical analysis of teleportation-based quantum error correction under realistic noise models. By explicitly distinguishing between ideal and noisy teleportation channels, the role of teleportation in QEC is clarified and the relative performance of the three-qubit repetition code, Shor code, and Steane code is assessed within a consistent simulation framework.

2 Methodology

This section describes the theoretical framework and numerical procedures employed to investigate teleportation-based quantum error correction under realistic noise conditions. The methodology is designed to clearly separate the effects of noise arising during teleportation from those mitigated through quantum error correction codes.

2.1 Quantum Teleportation Framework

The standard quantum teleportation protocol forms the basis of this work [2]. An arbitrary single-qubit quantum state

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle, \quad (1)$$

is transferred from a sender (Alice) to a receiver (Bob) using a shared maximally entangled Bell state

$$|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle) \quad (2)$$

Alice performs a joint Bell-state measurement on the input qubit and her half of the entangled pair. The resulting classical outcomes are communicated to Bob through a classical channel, upon which Bob applies conditional Pauli operations to reconstruct the original quantum state. In the absence of noise, the protocol ideally achieves unit fidelity [2].

Figure 2: Workflow of teleportation-based quantum error correction employed in this work. An arbitrary input state is first encoded using a quantum error correction code, teleported through a noisy quantum channel, decoded, and corrected at the receiver before fidelity evaluation.

2.2 Noise Modeling and Quantum Channels

To emulate realistic quantum hardware conditions, noise is introduced during the teleportation process using standard quantum channel models commonly employed in quantum information theory [4]. The following noise mechanisms are considered:

- Bit-flip noise, represented by Pauli- X errors
- Phase-flip noise, represented by Pauli- Z errors

- Combined bit-and-phase errors, represented by Pauli- Y errors
- Amplitude damping, modeling energy relaxation
- Phase damping, modeling pure dephasing

Each noise process is characterized by a noise probability p and is applied manually at specific stages of the teleportation circuit to isolate its influence on teleportation fidelity.

2.3 Teleportation-Based Quantum Error Correction

Quantum error correction is implemented by encoding logical qubits into entangled states of multiple physical qubits prior to teleportation. The encoded logical states are teleported as composite systems, followed by decoding and correction operations at the receiver [4].

The following quantum error correction codes are investigated:

- Three-qubit repetition code, which protects against single bit-flip errors
- Shor code, capable of correcting both bit-flip and phase-flip errors
- Steane code, which corrects arbitrary single-qubit errors using the stabilizer formalism

Syndrome information is inferred through teleportation-based operations, and appropriate correction operators are applied conditionally based on the detected error patterns.

2.4 Simulation Procedure

All teleportation and error correction protocols are implemented using numerical quantum circuit simulations in Python. Noise is introduced manually through probabilistic error operations rather than device-specific noise models, enabling precise control over error types and noise strengths [3].

The simulation workflow consists of the following steps:

1. Preparation of the input quantum state $|\psi\rangle$
2. Encoding of the logical qubit using a chosen QEC code
3. Teleportation of the encoded state through a noisy quantum channel
4. Decoding and application of error correction operations
5. Reconstruction of the output state at the receiver

This approach allows a consistent comparison between unprotected teleportation and teleportation-based quantum error correction schemes under identical noise conditions.

2.5 Fidelity Evaluation

The performance of each protocol is quantified using the state fidelity

$$F = \langle \psi | \rho_{\text{out}} | \psi \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where ρ_{out} denotes the density matrix of the reconstructed output state at Bob's end.

Fidelity values are averaged over multiple noise realizations to reduce statistical fluctuations. The results are compared across different error correction codes to assess their effectiveness in mitigating teleportation-induced noise.

2.6 Comparative Analysis Framework

To ensure a fair comparison, all teleportation and quantum error correction schemes are evaluated under identical noise strengths and circuit conditions wherever possible. The trade-off between fidelity improvement and circuit overhead is analyzed to assess the practical feasibility of teleportation-based quantum error correction in near-term noisy intermediate-scale quantum devices [3].

3 Results

In this section, we present numerical results obtained from simulations of teleportation-based quantum error correction under realistic noise models. The performance of different error correction codes is evaluated using the teleportation fidelity as a function of the physical error probability p . For each code, results are shown for both ideal teleportation, which serves as an upper bound, and noisy teleportation, which incorporates additional teleportation-induced errors.

3.1 Repetition Code

Figure 3 shows the teleportation fidelity for the three-qubit repetition code under ideal and noisy teleportation channels. In the ideal teleportation limit, the fidelity decreases smoothly with increasing p due to noise acting on the encoded physical qubits. When teleportation-induced noise is included, a systematic reduction in fidelity is observed across the entire range of error probabilities.

The approximately uniform separation between the ideal and noisy curves reflects the fixed contribution of teleportation-related errors. Although the repetition code only protects against bit-flip errors, teleportation-based error correction provides a noticeable improvement over unprotected teleportation in the low-noise regime, consistent with expectations for low-overhead codes in noisy environments [4].

Figure 3: Teleportation fidelity as a function of physical error probability p for teleportation-based quantum error correction using the three-qubit repetition code. Results are shown for ideal and noisy teleportation channels.

3.2 Shor Code

The performance of teleportation-based quantum error correction using Shor’s code is shown in Fig. 4. Shor’s code achieves high fidelity at low physical error probabilities, consistent with its ability to correct both bit-flip and phase-flip errors [4].

Figure 4: Teleportation fidelity as a function of physical error probability p for teleportation-based quantum error correction using the Shor code. Results are shown for ideal teleportation, which provides an upper bound on performance, and noisy teleportation, which includes additional teleportation-induced errors.

However, as the noise strength increases, the fidelity decreases more rapidly than in the repetition-code case. This behavior can be attributed to the larger circuit depth and nine-qubit encoding required by Shor’s code, which leads to increased accumulation of errors during the teleportation process. The inclusion of teleportation-induced noise further lowers the achievable fidelity, emphasizing the sensitivity of high-overhead codes to imperfections in teleportation operations, particularly in near-term noisy quantum devices [3].

3.3 Steane Code

Figure 5 presents the teleportation fidelity obtained using the Steane code under ideal and noisy teleportation conditions. Among the codes studied, the Steane code exhibits a favorable balance between error-correction capability and circuit overhead. Across the inves-

Figure 5: Teleportation fidelity as a function of physical error probability p for teleportation-based quantum error correction using the Steane code. Results are shown for ideal teleportation and noisy teleportation channels.

igated noise range, the Steane code consistently achieves higher fidelity than Shor’s code while correcting arbitrary single-qubit errors using fewer physical qubits. Compared to the repetition code, the Steane code provides improved protection against combined error mechanisms, particularly in the presence of phase and amplitude damping, in agreement with the expected advantages of CSS-type stabilizer codes [4].

3.4 Summary of Results

The numerical results demonstrate that teleportation-based quantum error correction improves the fidelity of quantum teleportation across all considered noise strengths. For each error correction code, ideal teleportation establishes an upper bound on achievable fidelity, while noisy teleportation captures the impact of imperfections inherent to realistic teleportation protocols.

Among the studied schemes, the repetition code provides modest protection in the low-noise regime but is limited to correcting bit-flip errors. Shor’s code achieves high fidelity at low error probabilities but exhibits a faster degradation with increasing noise due to its larger qubit overhead. The Steane code consistently attains higher fidelity than Shor’s code across the investigated noise range, reflecting a favorable balance between error-correction capability and circuit complexity.

These results highlight the importance of accounting for both error-correction strength and implementation overhead when designing teleportation-based quantum error correction protocols. A detailed comparative discussion of these trade-offs is presented in the following section.

4 Discussion

In this section, we discuss the implications of the numerical results obtained for teleportation-based quantum error correction and provide a comparative analysis of the different error correction codes studied. The discussion focuses on the trade-offs between error-correction capability, circuit overhead, and robustness to teleportation-induced noise.

4.1 Comparative Performance of Teleportation-Based QEC Codes

Figure 6 presents a direct comparison of the teleportation fidelity achieved using the repetition, Shor, and Steane codes under noisy teleportation conditions. Only noisy teleportation results are considered here, as they represent the most realistic operational regime for near term quantum device [3]. At low physical error probabilities, all three codes provide high

Figure 6: Comparative teleportation fidelity as a function of physical error probability p for teleportation-based quantum error correction using the repetition, Shor, and Steane codes under noisy teleportation conditions.

teleportation fidelity, with the repetition and Steane codes outperforming Shor’s code. As the noise strength increases, the fidelity of all schemes decreases monotonically; however, the rate of degradation differs significantly across codes.

The repetition code exhibits relatively stable performance due to its minimal circuit depth and low qubit overhead, despite its limited ability to correct only bit-flip errors. In contrast, Shor’s code, while capable of correcting both bit-flip and phase-flip errors, suffers from rapid fidelity degradation as noise increases. This behavior arises from the larger number of physical qubits and gates required for encoding and decoding, which leads to increased noise accumulation during the teleportation process, a well known limitation of high overhead codes in noisy environments [4].

The Steane code consistently achieves higher fidelity than Shor’s code across the investigated noise range and performs competitively with the repetition code at higher error probabilities. This indicates that the Steane code offers a favorable balance between error-correction strength and implementation overhead in teleportation-based settings, consistent with expectations for CSS type stabilizer codes [4].

4.2 Impact of Teleportation-Induced Noise

An important observation from the results is the systematic reduction in teleportation fidelity when teleportation-induced noise is included. Even in the absence of physical noise on the encoded qubits, imperfect teleportation operations introduce a finite reduction in fidelity. As physical noise increases, teleportation-induced errors compound with errors accumulated during encoding and decoding.

These findings highlight that teleportation fidelity is influenced not only by the choice of error correction code but also by the quality of the teleportation protocol itself. Consequently, optimizing teleportation operations is essential for realizing the full benefits of teleportation-based quantum error correction, it also emphasized in recent studies of noise resilient teleportation protocols [7].

4.3 Implications for Near-Term Quantum Devices

The comparative analysis suggests that, in the noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) regime, lower-overhead error correction codes can outperform more powerful codes with higher resource requirements. While Shor’s code provides theoretical protection against arbitrary single-qubit errors, its practical performance is limited by the accumulated noise arising from increased circuit complexity [3].

The Steane code emerges as a promising candidate for teleportation-based error correction in near-term devices, as it combines the ability to correct general single-qubit errors with moderate qubit overhead. These results emphasize that effective quantum error correction in teleportation-based protocols must balance correction capability with realistic implementation constraints.

4.4 Limitations and Outlook

The present study employs phenomenological noise models and idealized decoding operations, without incorporating hardware-specific noise parameters or fault-tolerant syndrome extraction. While this approach enables clear comparisons between different error correction schemes, future work could extend the analysis to device-calibrated noise models, repeated syndrome measurements, and topological error correction codes.

Nevertheless, the results provide valuable insights into the performance of teleportation-based quantum error correction under realistic noise conditions and establish a framework for evaluating trade-offs between different coding strategies. Recent experimental and theoretical progress in teleportation and quantum error correction suggests that such analyses will play an important role in guiding the design of scalable and noise-resilient quantum architectures [2] [5].

5 Conclusion

In this work, we presented a numerical study of teleportation-based quantum error correction under realistic noise models. By explicitly distinguishing between ideal and noisy telepor-

tation channels, we analyzed how imperfections in the teleportation process influence the effectiveness of different quantum error correction codes.

The performance of the three-qubit repetition code, Shor code, and Steane code was systematically evaluated using teleportation fidelity as a function of physical error probability. While ideal teleportation provides an upper bound on achievable performance, noisy teleportation reveals the practical impact of teleportation-induced errors in near-term quantum settings [3].

Our results show that teleportation-based quantum error correction can significantly improve fidelity in the low- and intermediate-noise regimes. However, the effectiveness of a given code is governed by a trade-off between error-correction capability and circuit overhead. In particular, high-overhead codes such as the Shor code are more susceptible to accumulated noise during teleportation, whereas lower-overhead codes exhibit greater robustness in the presence of realistic imperfections, consistent with established principles of quantum error correction [4].

Among the codes studied, the Steane code demonstrates a favorable balance between error-correction strength and implementation complexity, achieving consistently high fidelity across the investigated noise range. These findings highlight the importance of selecting error correction strategies that are well-matched to the constraints of teleportation-based protocols and near-term noisy quantum devices.

Although the simulations presented here are hardware-agnostic, the considered noise models capture key error mechanisms relevant to superconducting qubit platforms, including energy relaxation, dephasing, and effective Pauli errors. As a result, the observed trends are qualitatively applicable to superconducting quantum processors, where teleportation-based primitives are expected to play an important role in modular and distributed architectures [2] [5].

Future work may extend this framework to device-calibrated noise parameters, explicit modeling of superconducting qubit gate and measurement errors, fault-tolerant syndrome extraction, and topological quantum error correction codes, providing further insight into the scalability of teleportation-based quantum error correction schemes.

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